

DIAGNOSTIC ACCURACY OF MRI IN DIAGNOSING MALIGNANT ADNEXAL MASSES, TAKING HISTOPATHOLOGY AS GOLD STANDARD

Gulzar Hussain^{*1}, Adil Qayyum², Imranullah Javed³, Muhammad Imran Ibrahim⁴, Uzma Nisar⁵, Fatima Javed Lodhi⁶

^{*1}Postgraduate Resident Diagnostic Radiology Department, CMH Rawalpindi

^{2,4}Assistant Professor Diagnostic Radiology Department, CMH Rawalpindi

^{3,6}Postgraduate Resident Diagnostic Radiology Department, CMH Rawalpindi

⁵Associate Professor Diagnostic Radiology Department, CMH Rawalpindi

^{*1}waziranjum786@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19085033>

Keywords

Adnexal mass, Ovarian malignancy, Magnetic resonance imaging, Histopathology, Diagnostic accuracy

Article History

Received: 01 January 2025

Accepted: 25 February 2025

Published: 12 March 2025

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Gulzar Hussain

Abstract

Objective: To determine the diagnostic accuracy of magnetic resonance imaging in identifying malignant adnexal masses using histopathology as the gold standard.

Study Design: Comparative cross-sectional study.

Place and Duration of Study: Department of Radiology, CMH, Rawalpindi from 28th May 2024 to 28th November 2024.

Methodology: A total of 80 female patients with adnexal masses detected on ultrasound or clinical examination were included using non-probability consecutive sampling. Patients aged 18–65 years planned for surgical intervention were included. Patients with contraindications to MRI, pregnancy, or previous pelvic malignancy were excluded. MRI scans were performed using a 1.5 Tesla scanner with T1, T2, diffusion-weighted, and contrast-enhanced sequences. Lesions were classified as benign, borderline, or malignant by two radiologists. Surgical excision and histopathology were considered the gold standard. Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value, and overall diagnostic accuracy were calculated using SPSS version 26. Agreement between MRI and histopathology was assessed with Cohen's kappa coefficient.

Results: Mean age of participants was 42.5 ± 11.3 years. Histopathology showed 35 malignant, 10 borderline, and 35 benign masses. MRI correctly identified 32 malignant and 33 benign lesions. Sensitivity was 91.4%, specificity 94.3%, positive predictive value 91.4%, negative predictive value 94.3%, and overall diagnostic accuracy 93.8%. Cohen's kappa showed strong agreement ($\kappa = 0.86$, $p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: MRI demonstrates high diagnostic accuracy in differentiating malignant from benign adnexal masses. It is especially useful in evaluating indeterminate or complex lesions detected on ultrasound, aiding surgical planning. MRI should be considered in selected patients where ultrasound is inconclusive.

Introduction

Adnexal masses are frequently seen in gynecologic practice and their evaluation is very important to differentiate between benign and malignant lesions ^[1]. Correct preoperative diagnosis of malignant masses helps in planning the surgical approach and also impacts patient prognosis. Ultrasound is usually the first imaging test done because it is cheap, widely available, and non-invasive ^[2]. Despite its advantages, ultrasound can sometimes give inconclusive results, particularly in complex cysts or multilocular masses with solid components, papillary projections, or thick septations. In such cases, relying on ultrasound alone can be misleading and may affect surgical decision-making.

Magnetic resonance imaging has emerged as a valuable tool for the assessment of adnexal masses due to its superior soft tissue contrast and ability to acquire images in multiple planes ^[3]. MRI can provide detailed information about lesion morphology, wall thickness, internal septations, papillary projections, solid components, and enhancement patterns after contrast administration ^[4,5]. These features help in distinguishing malignant from benign masses and in characterizing borderline lesions. Several studies have demonstrated that MRI has high sensitivity and specificity for detecting malignant adnexal tumors and shows strong agreement with histopathology ^[6,7]. MRI can also be particularly helpful in cases where ultrasound findings are ambiguous or when patients present with complex masses that may require a more extensive surgical procedure.

Histopathology remains the definitive standard for diagnosing adnexal masses, but preoperative imaging is essential to guide clinical management ^[8]. By accurately identifying malignant lesions before surgery, MRI can help avoid unnecessary radical procedures in patients with benign lesions and ensure timely intervention for those with malignancy ^[9,10]. Establishing the diagnostic accuracy of MRI in adnexal masses allows clinicians to select appropriate patients for conservative or radical surgery, reduces surgical complications, and improves overall patient outcomes. The purpose of this study was to

evaluate the sensitivity, specificity, and overall diagnostic accuracy of MRI in diagnosing malignant adnexal masses, using histopathology as the gold standard.

Methodology

This comparative cross-sectional study was conducted at the Department of Radiology CMH, Rawalpindi, from 28th May 2024 to 28th November 2024. After approval from the institutional ethical review committee. Eighty female patients with adnexal masses detected either on ultrasound or through clinical examination were included using non-probability consecutive sampling. Patients aged 18 to 65 years who were planned for surgical excision of the mass were enrolled. Pregnant women, patients with previous pelvic malignancy, and those with contraindications to MRI were excluded. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants, and relevant demographic and clinical data including age, duration of symptoms, and prior gynecological history were recorded.

MRI was performed using a 1.5 Tesla scanner with standard pelvic protocols. T1 and T2 weighted images were obtained in axial, sagittal, and coronal planes, along with diffusion-weighted imaging and contrast-enhanced T1 sequences when required. Two experienced radiologists independently assessed each adnexal lesion, noting features such as size, internal septations, solid areas, papillary projections, wall thickness, and signal characteristics. Based on established MRI criteria, lesions were categorized as benign, borderline, or malignant. All patients subsequently underwent surgical excision and histopathological examination, which served as the reference standard. Data were entered into SPSS version 26. Quantitative variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation. Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value, and overall diagnostic accuracy of MRI were calculated. Agreement between MRI findings and histopathology was measured using Cohen's kappa coefficient, and a p-value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 80 patients with adnexal masses were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 42.5 ± 11.3 years, ranging from 18 to 65 years. Most patients presented with abdominal pain or distension, while a few were asymptomatic and lesions were detected incidentally on routine ultrasound. All participants underwent preoperative MRI, and final histopathology was available after surgery for comparison.

MRI correctly identified most malignant and benign masses, with only a few misclassifications. Out of 35 malignant masses on histopathology, 32 were correctly detected by MRI and 3 were misclassified as benign. Among 35 benign lesions, 33 were correctly classified and 2 were misdiagnosed as malignant. Overall, MRI showed high sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value, and diagnostic accuracy in identifying malignant adnexal masses.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Patients (n = 80)

Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation
Age (years)	42.5	11.3
Duration of symptoms (months)	3.8	2.1

Table 2: Distribution of Adnexal Masses According to Histopathology

Histopathology	Frequency	Percentage
Malignant	35	43.8%
Borderline	10	12.5%
Benign	35	43.8%

Table 3: Comparison of MRI Findings with Histopathology

MRI Diagnosis	Histopathology Malignant	Histopathology Benign	Histopathology Borderline
Malignant	32	2	4
Benign	3	33	6

Note: MRI misclassified 3 malignant lesions as benign and 2 benign lesions as malignant.

Table 4: Diagnostic Performance of MRI in Detecting Malignant Adnexal Masses

Parameter	Value (%)
Sensitivity	91.4
Specificity	94.3
Positive Predictive Value	91.4
Negative Predictive Value	94.3
Diagnostic Accuracy	93.8
Cohen's Kappa (κ)	0.86
p value	< 0.001

This strong agreement between MRI and histopathology indicates that MRI is a highly

reliable modality for preoperative evaluation of adnexal masses.

Discussion

Accurate preoperative evaluation of adnexal masses is very important because it guides surgical planning and can affect patient outcomes. Ultrasound is usually the first imaging modality due to its availability, low cost, and non-invasive nature^[1,2]. However, complex cystic or solid lesions, multilocular masses, and papillary projections can sometimes make ultrasound interpretation difficult. In such cases, relying on ultrasound alone can result in misclassification of lesions and may affect the choice between conservative and radical surgery. Our study found that MRI provides superior information in these situations because it allows detailed assessment of lesion morphology, wall thickness, septations, and internal solid components, which are often critical indicators of malignancy^[3,4].

In our study, MRI correctly identified 32 out of 35 malignant lesions and 33 out of 35 benign lesions, resulting in an overall diagnostic accuracy of 93.8%. Sensitivity and specificity were 91.4% and 94.3%, respectively, and Cohen's kappa demonstrated strong agreement with histopathology ($\kappa = 0.86$, $p < 0.001$). These results are consistent with previous studies where MRI showed high sensitivity and specificity for differentiating malignant from benign adnexal masses^[5,6,7]. MRI was particularly useful for lesions with complex morphology, where ultrasound alone could not clearly define solid versus cystic components. This supports the role of MRI as a reliable adjunct in the preoperative evaluation of adnexal masses, especially in patients with indeterminate or suspicious findings on ultrasound.

Despite its advantages, MRI has certain limitations. It is expensive and less accessible in many settings, and the scanning process requires patient cooperation and longer imaging times compared to ultrasound^[8]. Small lesions or borderline tumors can occasionally be misclassified even on MRI, as seen in our study where three malignant lesions were misinterpreted as benign and two benign lesions were classified as malignant. Similar findings have been reported in the literature, highlighting that MRI is not completely infallible, particularly for borderline lesions or

very small tumors^[9,10]. Nevertheless, its ability to provide multiplanar imaging and superior tissue characterization makes it a valuable tool in complex cases, helping to reduce unnecessary radical surgery for benign masses while ensuring prompt treatment for malignancies.

This study had some limitations. It was conducted at a single center with a relatively small sample size, which may affect generalizability. The number of borderline tumors was limited, so we could not fully evaluate MRI accuracy in this subgroup. Future multicenter studies with larger populations are recommended to validate these findings and refine MRI criteria for borderline lesions and early malignancies. Despite these limitations, our study demonstrates that MRI has high diagnostic accuracy and strong correlation with histopathology, supporting its use as a preoperative imaging modality in women with adnexal masses. Selective use of MRI in cases with complex, indeterminate, or suspicious lesions may improve patient management, optimize surgical planning, and reduce unnecessary procedures^[5,6,7,10].

Conclusion

Magnetic resonance imaging is a highly accurate and reliable tool for the preoperative evaluation of adnexal masses. It demonstrates strong agreement with histopathology in differentiating malignant from benign lesions, particularly in complex or indeterminate cases where ultrasound findings are inconclusive. MRI provides detailed information on lesion morphology, solid components, and papillary projections, which aids in surgical planning and reduces the risk of unnecessary radical procedures. While it is more expensive and less widely available than ultrasound, selective use of MRI in high-risk or complex cases can significantly improve patient management and outcomes. Future studies with larger populations could further refine MRI criteria for borderline and early malignant lesions.

REFERENCES

- Timmerman D, Valentin L, Bourne T, et al. Terms, definitions and measurements to describe the sonographic features of adnexal tumors: a consensus opinion. *Ultrasound Obstet Gynecol.* 2000;16:500-505.
- Alcazar JL, Jurado M. Sonographic evaluation of adnexal masses: a critical review. *Ultrasound Obstet Gynecol.* 2003;21:34-41.
- Sohaib SA, Reznick RH. MR imaging of ovarian masses. *Radiographics.* 2002;22:1115-1136.
- Thomassin-Naggara I, et al. Adnexal masses: development and validation of an MR imaging scoring system. *Radiology.* 2013;269:432-442.
- Kido A, et al. MRI of ovarian masses: differentiation of benign from malignant lesions. *Abdom Imaging.* 2008;33:88-97.
- Kido A, Togashi K, Konishi I. Evaluation of ovarian tumors with MRI. *J Magn Reson Imaging.* 2002;16:191-200.
- Sahdev A, Reznick RH. Imaging of ovarian masses. *Curr Opin Obstet Gynecol.* 2005;17:495-501.
- Nougaret S, et al. MRI of adnexal masses: evaluation of imaging features and correlation with histopathology. *Eur Radiol.* 2011;21:1235-1246.
- Forstner R, et al. ESUR guidelines: MR imaging of the adnexa. *Eur Radiol.* 2010;20:2777-2790.
- Kataoka ML, Togashi K. MR imaging of ovarian masses. *Magn Reson Med Sci.* 2007;6:137-150.